

REDUCING LEGACY ATE SYSTEM SUSTAINMENT COSTS THROUGH MODERN SYSTEM ENGINEERING ARCHITECTURE CONCEPTS.

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Abstract - The cost of sustaining legacy automatic test systems is increasing. Obsolete and unsupported equipment create higher maintenance costs every year the systems are in operation. With a large dollar investment in the test program sets (TPS) and extended sustainment requirements beyond expected life cycle, a plan to sustain the test capability is needed.

A complete modernization of the test system at reduced cost can be achieved using the latest system engineering concepts. Object oriented design, commercial-off-the-shelf (COTS) hardware and software products reduce station costs dramatically. Preservation of a large legacy TPS investment drives specialized hardware selection criteria. Applying open architecture concepts and use of standardized bus architectures allows for multiple vendor selection and easier replacement of instrumentation when obsolete, minimizing future sustainment costs. Electronic technical manuals and voice command control integration combine to produce an end product that is easier to use and reduce training time for operating personnel. In-station calibration provides for easier maintenance.

Combining all the above concepts into a system engineering approach reduces development time, hardware costs, documentation costs, training and maintenance of a new station which will result in a dramatic cost savings for sustainment of the legacy system.

INTRODUCTION

Sustainment costs of legacy automatic test systems increases each year due to obsolete and unsupported equipment. The F16 Avionics Depot Analog test station design is based upon 1960s-1970s technology and instrumentation. The instrumentation for this station has become obsolete, and mostly unsupported. The requirement to support the F16 to the year 2020 has pushed the test station beyond its

expected life cycle. Requirements to sustain this equipment for support capability beyond its expected life cycle increases the maintenance costs substantially each year it is extended, with the possibility of catastrophic failure eminent. Due to the state of the current test stations, a solution to the problem was needed quickly. This paper presents an approach to sustain the legacy system by applying new system engineering concepts in refurbishing the test station, reducing overall cost of refurbishment, minimizing development time and effort and easing future maintenance support costs.

REHOST VERSUS REFURBISHMENT

The cost of replacing a legacy automatic test station with a new system involves replacement of the test equipment and rehosting the Test Program Set (TPS) to the new equipment. The TPS includes test software and the interface adapter for the test station. The Analog Test Station supports over 220 TPS. Rehost costs involve new test adapter design and developing software in the new test station environment. The analysis of rehosting TPSs onto new equipment vs. using the existing TPSs on updated equipment revealed an interesting result. Test station hardware costs are inexpensive compared to rehost costs for 220 TPSs. From this awareness, the concept of designing a test station around TPS requirements was formed.

The TPS language is composed of ATLAS and two other languages, an intermediate higher level language and an assembly style language. These would be required to be rehosted to another test

language, or keep compatibility and supportability on the new target station. Due to the nature of the ATLAS and other two languages, it was determined that C would be the target language due to its flexibility and availability of software development tools.

SYSTEM ENGINEERING APPROACH

Object-Oriented Software Design to Reduce Development Time

The design of the system begins with the approach for software. An object-oriented approach to software design allows for easier maintenance, a more structured approach, and faster development time. Two major software development areas where object-oriented design was incorporated are the instrument drivers and TPS ATLAS to C translation.

Instrument Drivers. For the instrument driver, objects are defined by TPS resources. The TPS resource object structure uses common data information and error structures for passing information to and from the test station. By using common structures, the development of one TPS resource had very similar coding to any other TPS resource and thus development time is reduced through code reuse. Instrument drivers using Plug and Play drivers developed by vendors also decreased development time. In cases where vendors followed the Plug and Play specifications defined by the Plug and Play consortium, development time was also significantly reduced, once one of the initial TPS drivers were developed.

ATLAS to C Translator. For TPS translation, the use of object oriented tools to develop a code translator were used. The use of LEX and YACC to facilitate translation code development met the requirements for an object-oriented approach. LEX and YACC were chosen because they are object-oriented compiler development tools, and they are free to the public from the Internet. The use of these tools in compiler development provided a structured development environment and reduced development costs significantly.

Commercial-off-the-Shelf Products Reduce Hardware and Software Costs

Use of commercial software and hardware products allows the reduction in cost, due to the minimization of development costs.

Software. In this project, National Instruments Test Executive™ was used for test station control. The availability of this product's source code allowed modifications to the product to minimize impact to the operation of the test station. By making Test Executive™ look and act similar to the old test station, less training time is needed for the station operators to learn the operation of the new station. Also, since the bulk of the Test Executive™ functions were already developed, minimal development time was needed and thus reduced cost for development.

TPS driven Hardware requirements. Original test station specifications were used for the baseline hardware design requirements. However, the resources in the existing test station were not fully utilized by the TPSs. Since a one for one replacement for each instrument is not available on the market today for a specialized instrument in the existing test station, requirements by the TPSs were used to modify the design requirements where the functionality was excessive. By doing so, the specialized instrumentation was no longer needed and COTS equipment was available to meet the requirements. The availability of the COTS equipment is much less expensive than having a vendor create a new specialty piece of instrumentation. Also, future supportability will be more likely available with a standard commercial product than a specialized unique product. Thus by using COTS equipment test station hardware costs were dramatically reduced.

Standardized bus architectures

The original test station contained a proprietary bus and station software. This made hardware and software upgrades very difficult and very expensive. Availability of standardized bus architectures such as VXI and GPIB allow an open architecture where instruments from multiple vendors are available to accomplish the same function. This allows identification of multiple sources for purchase of instrumentation. With multiple sources available, there is less likelihood of instrumentation quickly becoming obsolete and unsupported. If instrumentation does become unavailable, it is likely that a similar

instrument is available from that vendor, or from another vendor. With the addition of the Plug and Play consortium to form a standard on driver development, virtually eliminates any proprietary software in the test station. This allows future maintenance costs and sustainment costs to be minimized by providing multiple vendors and products to be available for replacement.

above allows refurbishment of test station to be done more cost effectively and with less development time. Using modern software techniques and hardware in test station design will ease future maintenance issues and thus reduce overall sustainment costs.

Modern Integrated Improvements

With the advent of the computer and Windows™ environment, improvements to the existing system can be integrated without much extra time, effort and minimal cost. Documentation and technical manuals are authored with software on computer. With the open environment of the PC and Windows™, integration of electronic documents and technical manuals with the test executive is easily done. Other unique advances have been made in the areas of Voice recognition. Voice command control of the test station has been integrated using free software available on the Internet. Data collection has been automated and is available for statistical process control analysis to improve test performance.

In-station Calibration Provides Easier Maintenance

Calibration of the instrumentation is done in-station to reduce maintenance on the instrumentation. By not removing equipment for calibration, less potential for damage and more accuracy for final calibration are available to the maintenance personnel. VXI chassis' are designed for minimal insertion and removal of instrumentation. In-station calibration reduces the wear and tear on the components and will provide a longer MTBF. Calibration of the instrumentation in a VXI chassis also may rely on the internal timing clock of that specific chassis. If timing is critical to a calibrated measurement, using a different VXI chassis for calibration may induce unexpected error into the measurement.

SUMMARY

In summary, by refurbishing automatic test systems with modern instrumentation, sustainment of legacy systems will meet the requirements for future support. The use of the system engineering approach outlined